

The different roles of learning recent and accumulative statistics

Aviel Sulem¹ and Merav Ahissar^{1,2}

We perceive key aspects of familiar environments almost immediately, while perception in unfamiliar environments is slower. In this review, we examine the distinct roles of recent versus accumulative long-term exposure in enabling this efficiency. Accumulative statistics underlie the formation of stable categories (e.g. syllables in our native language), whereas recent events bias our online predictions toward the current context. Typically developing individuals place greater weight on recent events than single earlier events, but also weight accumulative statistics. However, individuals with developmental atypicalities show atypical patterns of statistical learning: individuals with dyslexia tend to assign less weight to long-term statistics, which affects their long-term categories. By contrast, autistics utilize long-term statistics like neurotypicals, but are slower in updating their priors and motor plans by recent events, which reduces their flexibility. These observations suggest that the dynamics of statistical learning impact the strengths and weaknesses of people's social and cognitive skill acquisition.

Addresses

¹ The Edmond and Lily Safra Center for Brain Sciences, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Jerusalem 9190401, Israel

² Department of Psychology, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Jerusalem 9190401, Israel

Corresponding author: Ahissar, Merav (merav.ahissar@mail.huji.ac.il)

Current Opinion in Neurobiology 2025, 93:103072

This review comes from a themed issue on **Systems Neuroscience 2025**

Edited by **Robert Froemke, Máté Lengyel, József Fiser and Livia de Hoz**

For complete overview of the section, please refer the article collection - [Systems Neuroscience 2025](#)

Available online 28 June 2025

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conb.2025.103072>

0959-4388/© 2025 The Authors. Published by Elsevier Ltd. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Learning environmental statistics through exposure is essential for skill acquisition and expert behavior [1]. Although serial discrimination tasks (Figure 1) were originally developed to measure perceptual sensitivity in isolation from contextual influences (e.g. Ref. [2]), later

studies revealed that these tasks are not bias free (e.g. Ref. [3]). As such, they offer a powerful framework for examining the formation of predictions based on history [4]. Importantly, these tasks enable a dissociation between the bias generated by recent events (recency bias) versus the bias generated by accumulative history (long-term bias) [5], although when the statistics are stable, recent and earlier history are generally correlated. This distinction is important because different timescales reflect distinct dynamics of the environment's statistics, which in turn support different behavioral demands.

Long-term statistics improve perceptual representations in stable environments

Evidence for the impact of long-term accumulation of environmental statistics was first documented in the early 20th century [6], where it was referred to as *central tendency*. The basic observation was that participants asked to memorize the size of cards made systematic errors in their estimations: they tended to overestimate smaller cards and underestimate larger ones. This pattern was interpreted as a contraction in the participants' perceptual judgments toward the mean of the card-size distribution. Since then, numerous studies have replicated this result across various stimuli and modalities (e.g. Refs. [7,8]), including for the perception of time [9,10].

This contraction toward the mean, which is often explained in a Bayesian framework [7,11], is part of the gradual acquisition of a prototypical representation of stimulus features. The Bayesian account holds that noisy representations of the current stimulus (the likelihood function) are integrated with prior knowledge about the stimulus distribution (the prior) to optimize perception towards the most likely stimulus given the (partial) evidence. The noisier the sensory representation relative to the reliability of the prior, the stronger the contraction toward the prior's mean. Studies have consistently shown that increasing sensory or memory noise amplifies this contraction [8,12,13].

Evidence from perceptual [5] and sensorimotor [14] studies suggests that in stable environments, good performers do not merely learn the mean of the stimulus distribution, but rather appear to capture aspects of its shape or variability (Figure 2a–c). Learning these key

Figure 1

Schematic illustration of a two-tone pitch discrimination task. Each trial (t) consists of two sequentially presented pure tones, separated by a silent inter-stimulus interval (ISI). The pitch interval between the two tones is defined as $\delta^t = \log_2(f_2^t) - \log_2(f_1^t)$ (in octaves), where f_1^t and f_2^t are the frequencies of the first and second tone in trial t . Participants are asked to indicate whether the first or the second tone has a higher pitch. Visual feedback is provided immediately after participants' response. Following an inter-trial interval (ITI), the next trial begins. The figure also illustrates the previous trial ($t - 1$), and key quantities derived from stimulus history. The variable d_1 represents the distance between the first tone of the current trial (f_1^t) and the mean of the two tones of the previous trial, reflecting the potential effect of recent history. The cumulative mean frequency $\langle f \rangle$ computed across all previous trials reflects accumulative statistics. The distance between f_1^t and $\langle f \rangle$ is denoted as d_∞ . Both d_1 and d_∞ capture statistical regularities that bias the perceptual representation of the first tone in the current trial, which can lead to systematic errors when comparing it to the second tone.

aspects is particularly advantageous when the stimulus distribution is complex. For example, in a bimodal distribution, participants' perception is not contracted toward the global mean frequency – whose probability is zero – but instead toward the means of the local modes (Figure 3a, left panel) [5,14].

Participants typically approximate optimal behavior, as evaluated (following Jaffe-Dax et al. [15]) by comparing their long-term bias to that predicted by an ideal Bayesian listener model (dashed black curves in Figures 2 and 3, left panels). This model assumes full prior knowledge of the stable stimulus distribution, which enables optimal decisions based on the listener's noise level. Although the stimulus distributions used in experimental settings are simple (e.g., uniform, Gaussian), they serve as controlled models for isolating core mechanisms of statistical learning. In some cases, they are similar to natural distributions, such as the case of orientation distribution, which is bimodally distributed around horizontal and vertical axes [16]. The close correspondence in bias shape and magnitude between participants and the ideal observer suggests that participants learn the distribution and weight the prior appropriately according to their sensory noise level.

Recent statistics are informative when the environment's statistics change

Language has stable statistical characteristics that are learned over years (e.g. syllabic frequency). Yet real-time communication is heavily influenced by local context. For example, during a conversation, speakers may change accents, use of words, and intonation, all of

which requires the listeners' speech perception to adapt to these immediate changes [17,18]. This adaptive process makes it possible to update speech predictions based on recent stimuli [19].

Perception is biased by recent context, a phenomenon known as *serial effects* or *serial dependence*, where the current perception or action is biased toward recent experiences [20,21]. Out of the various factors shaping recent experiences, such as response inertia (the tendency to repeat the same motor trajectory) [22] or decision-making processes (the tendency to repeat the same response) [23], here we focus on the influence of recent stimuli on perceptual judgments, which are referred to below as *recency bias*.

Sensory biases in the visual modality have been reported across a range of features, from simple ones such as orientation [24] and position [25], to more complex categories such as facial identity [26], facial expression [27], and facial attractiveness [28]. Biases from recent stimuli have also been observed in olfactory [29] and auditory perception [5,30–32]. These biases are interpreted as helping to maintain perceptual stability in spite of external changes [24,33,34].

As shown in Figure 2, Generalized Additive Models (GAM) [35,36] permit calculation of the recency bias function [5]. This type of analysis reveals very similar “tuning” functions across different stimulus distributions (Figure 2b–d; Figure 3a, right). In pitch discrimination tasks, recency bias peaks when the frequency difference from the previous trial is about half an octave and diminishes with increasing distance, such that at

Figure 2

Long-term bias and recency bias estimated using Generalized Additive Model (GAM) for two different frequency distributions, in a two-tone pitch discrimination task. Pure tones were randomly sampled from either a uniform (top, **a, b**) or a Gaussian (bottom, **c, d**) distribution. The probability $Pr("f_2^t > f_1^t")$ of a participant reporting that the second tone (f_2^t) has a higher pitch on trial t was modeled using GAM regressions, where Φ is the standard normal cumulative distribution function, α_p^t is a participant-specific frequency sensitivity, which can change over time, $\delta^t = \log_2(f_2^t) - \log_2(f_1^t)$ is the log frequency difference between f_2^t and f_1^t , b_1^t and b_∞^t are the recency bias and long-term bias functions, respectively. **Panels a and c** display the inferred long-term bias statistics (b_∞) as a function of the frequency distance (in octaves) between the first tone in the current trial and the mean frequency of the distribution (d_∞). The long-term bias statistics reflects rich and optimal learning of the stimulus distribution, as evidenced by its alignment with the inferred bias of an ideal Bayesian listener (dashed black curves) who has full knowledge of the entire stimulus distribution. Within the uniform distribution (**a**), stimuli have an equal chance of appearing. However, near the boundaries, one can infer that a tone cannot be too high or too low. In the Gaussian distribution (**c**), most tones are centered around the mean. Hence, as the current tone deviates in either direction, it becomes more "contracted" toward the mean. **Panels b and d** show the inferred recency bias (b_1) as a function of the frequency distance (in octaves) between the first tone in the current trial and the previous trial mean (d_1). The bias due to recent stimuli peaks around half an octave, indicating that distant recent stimuli do not "contract" current perception. The pattern of recency bias is largely invariant to stimulus distribution. Error bars indicate 95% confidence intervals. (Adapted from Ref. [5]).

Figure 3

Long-term bias and recency bias functions in a two-tone pitch discrimination task estimated with GAM for neurotypicals, individuals with autism, and individual with dyslexia. Pure tones were randomly sampled from a bimodal-uniform distribution, illustrated at the bottom of the left panels. The magnitude of the recency bias (right) is plotted as a function of the frequency distance (in octaves) between the first tone in the current trial and the previous trial mean (d_1). In all groups, the bias peaks at around half an octave and decreases with further distance. Notably, the recency bias (right panels) of individuals with dyslexia (c) is similar to that of neurotypicals (a), whereas individuals with autism (b) presented reduced magnitude. The long-term bias (left panels) is shown as a function of the frequency distance between the first tone in the current trial and the mean of the distribution (d_∞). This bias is divided into two sub-functions, reflecting a learned distinction between the two categories of the bimodal distribution. Optimal learning of the distribution is assessed by comparing the inferred bias functions to that of an ideal Bayesian listener, which assumes full prior knowledge of the stimulus distribution and calculates the bias function given the listener's noise level using Bayesian inference. This analysis shows that neurotypicals (a) and individuals with autism (b) exhibit optimal learning of these categories, with bias functions closely matching those of their calculated ideal listeners. In contrast, individuals with dyslexia (c) show a significant deviation from the ideal listener's function, suggesting reduced capacity to learn the distribution. Error bars indicate the standard deviation. (Adapted from Ref. [5]).

a distance of an octave, recent stimuli do not bias perception. This shape of the recency bias function (a characteristic Derivative-of-Gaussian [24]), has also been observed in numerous studies in the visual modality (see e.g. Ref. [20] for a review).

Adaptive learning dynamics in volatile environments

What is the optimal weighting of recent and earlier statistics? In stable environments, priors improve by accumulating more data over time. Learning the distribution of stimuli by giving equal weight to each exposure, and biasing perception toward their most likely stimulus is an optimal strategy. However, when the statistics change, it is better to update the priors by putting larger weights on more recent experiences (recency bias), since earlier information is less relevant. Thus, the optimal time window (relative weights of earlier stimuli) for learning statistics depends on the volatility (the rate of change of the stimulus distribution) of the environment [37]. Ideally, we would adapt our use of prior experiences to match the rate at which the environment changes [38–40].

Although higher volatility indeed increases the rate of decisional learning [41], it remains unclear whether this also applies to updating perceptual priors. The mechanisms underlying such adaptation of the learning rate are not fully understood, though anatomically, they have been attributed to specific medio-frontal regions such as the anterior cingulate cortex [41,42]. In any event, people's ability to adapt the weighting of bias is limited, as evidenced by persistent recency bias effects (i.e., a larger bias from the most recent event) even in statistically stable environments (e.g. Ref. [43]).

Relatedly, it remains unclear whether people can effectively switch between different patterns of previously learned statistics as they change. Specifically, can we accessibly store more than one set of contingencies in a given environment, and when relevant, only retrieve a previously learned set of contingencies rather than re-learn them? Recent analyses of sensorimotor learning suggest that we can do so [44], differentiating between “real learning” of new contingencies and identifying a previously learned set and retrieving it [45].

Atypical dynamics of learning environmental statistics are linked to atypical skill acquisition

Given that efficiency in accumulating statistics is important for mastering tasks that rely on stable statistics, whereas the efficiency of recency bias is mainly relevant for tasks that depend on fast updating of priors, it is likely that specific atypicalities in these learning mechanisms will affect the acquisition of different skills. As shown in the following sections, dyslexia — i.e.,

difficulties in acquiring expert reading skills — is associated with poor long-term accumulation of statistics, whereas autism — i.e., difficulties in acquiring expert social skills, which require the fast updating of plans and priors — is associated with weaker recency effects.

Dyslexia – weaker impact of long-term statistics

Developmental dyslexia is defined as a specific and persistent difficulty in becoming an expert reader despite substantial practice that cannot be attributed to a lack of general intelligence [46]. Consistent evidence over the last few decades has shown that verbal short-term memory is impaired in dyslexia. Yet, this atypicality was traditionally attributed to poor phonological representations [47]. Ahissar et al. [48,49] pioneered a view of dyslexia (the “anchoring-deficit hypothesis”) that poorer memory in dyslexia is not specific to speech sounds, and stems from the fast decay of their perceptual memory trace. This was shown to be specifically associated with dyslexia and not with other developmental atypicalities such as ADHD [50] or autism [5]. Jaffe-Dax et al. [15] found that perceptual memory decays faster in dyslexia in both serial discrimination (measured by bias magnitude) and in reading [51], where the benefits in reading time of repeated words decayed faster.

Lieder et al. [5] used GAM analyses to dissociate recent (Figures 2 and 3, right) and longer-term (Figures 2 and 3, left) biases under various (stable) distributions of stimulus frequencies. While no significant differences were found between individuals with dyslexia and typical readers in the shape and magnitude of recency bias (Figure 3, a vs. c, right), there was a significant group difference in the use of longer-term statistics (Figure 3, a vs. c, left) where typical readers exhibited an optimal long-term bias statistics. By contrast, individuals with dyslexia demonstrated a significantly lower and sub-optimally shaped long-term bias compared to the ideal listener.

The reduced ability to use long-term (measured within sessions) statistics in dyslexia is consistent with the fast decay of perceptual traces manifested in both EEG [51] and fMRI measures in perceptual visual [52] and auditory [53] regions. The reduced benefits from long-term perceptual statistics may lead to impoverished acquisition of perceptual categories (e.g. Refs. [54–56]), and to reduced short-term memory benefits from long-term familiarity [57–59]. While we propose a core deficit in dyslexia that underlies both phonological and non-phonological difficulties, this account is unlikely to explain all atypicalities that characterize individuals with dyslexia, as suggested by recent multifactorial causal models [60,61].

Autism – reduced impact of recent stimuli

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a highly diverse developmental condition, characterized by challenges in

social communication and interaction, along with restricted or repetitive behaviors and interests [46]. In this short review, we focus on high-functioning individuals with ASD, previously diagnosed with Asperger's Syndrome [62]. These individuals have typical linguistic and cognitive abilities, demonstrating adequate learning of both linguistic [63,64] and non-linguistic [65–67] categories. Understanding the neuro-cognitive mechanisms underlying autism has been highly challenging. Over the past 12 years, studies beginning with Pellicano & Burr [68] and followed by Friston et al. [69] have suggested that individuals with autism rely less on perceptual priors (e.g. Refs. [70–74]). Interestingly, atypical priors were also recorded in rodent models of autism [75].

Early studies of priors in autism suggested reduced susceptibility to perceptual illusions in autism [76], implying differences in long-term priors. Yet, this claim has been challenged by more recent work. For example, Mazuz et al. [77] found no reduction in susceptibility to visual illusions, and Noel et al. [78] reported that orientation biases near the cardinal axes, measured at the beginning of an orientation reproduction task, which reflects long-term (life-long) acquisition of natural orientation distribution is intact in autism.

Lieder et al. [5] used GAM analysis to dissociate the effects of recent versus accumulative statistics in a 2-tone pitch discrimination task. They found that autistic individuals, like neurotypicals, optimally learn various stable stimulus distributions. This was evidenced by the overlap between the inferred long-term bias function and that of an ideal Bayesian listener with full prior knowledge of the stimulus distribution. However, the weighting of recent stimuli was reduced in autism (Figure 3b, right) – though the tuning curve had the same shape, suggesting that the process is typical, but takes longer. Based on this observation, the authors proposed a “slow-update” deficit, where the reduced benefits from recent information limit autistic individuals' ability to respond at pace in changing environments. In line with these observations, Kurumada et al. [79] found a similar dissociation in speech prosody adaptation. Autistic adolescents accurately categorized basic prosodic meanings (distinguishing between statements and questions) but struggled to adapt to speaker-specific prosodic variations, which are critical for interpreting intention and meaning in everyday communication.

Studies in the motor domain have found an equivalent difficulty in the fast updating of motor plans [80,81]. It has also been suggested that individuals with autism have difficulties adapting the magnitude of their learning of priors to the rate at which the environment changes [82], perhaps due to their slow-updating (and

long adaptation), which undermines their flexibility to respond to change.

Together, these findings support a slow-update account of perceptual predictions and motor plans in autism, whereby recent stimulus representations are underweighted, leading to reduced flexibility in dynamic environments. This difficulty is neither purely sensory nor purely motor but reflects a challenge in using contextual changes to update the mapping between stimuli and responses. This interpretation is broadly compatible with predictive coding theories, which propose reduced precision-weighting of prediction errors [68]. However, our findings indicate that long-term statistical learning remains intact, pointing to a specific disruption in the integration of recent information rather than a general insensitivity to priors—at least in high-functioning individuals with autism. Interestingly, this account may also relate to challenges in causal inference, as described by Noel & Angelaki [83], who suggest that individuals with autism may have difficulty associating observations with their underlying causes.

Recency bias involves both top-down and bottom-up processes

It was suggested that serial dependence is driven by high-level representations of recent events, including object-level perceptual representations [26,27,84], post-perceptual decision-making processes [85], and working memory contributions [86]. According to the predictive coding framework [87], these representations should bias perception through top-down processes towards recently perceived objects, thus supporting perceptual stability [24,88]. Attention has also been shown to enhance the magnitude of the bias [24,89].

A recent study measured the contributions of high- and low-level processes, as well as top-down and bottom-up mechanisms, to recency bias in the context of pitch discrimination. The observed pattern of biases suggested that low-level memory components, operating in a bottom-up manner independently of recent percepts, also contributed to the pitch contraction [31,90]. Specifically, pitch contraction was stronger within timbre categories (Figure 4a), supporting the top-down account. However, across timbres, contraction was observed toward physically present (low-level) harmonics rather than abstract (high-level) pitch representations (Figure 4b), thus challenging the predictive coding hypothesis [90].

Taken together, these findings suggest that both top-down and bottom-up processes contribute to recency bias, operating at different levels of the perceptual and decisional hierarchy, and likely involving multiple neural mechanisms [91]. While an in-depth discussion is beyond

Figure 4

Top-down (a) and bottom-up (b) contributions to recency bias in pitch perception. **a. Top-down influence on pitch contraction – Pitch contraction is stronger within than across timbre categories.** In a two-tone pitch discrimination task with simple-tone and complex-tone trials intermixed, recency bias was calculated (using GAM) for each of the four types of consecutive trials (see legend). The curves show bias magnitude as a function of d_1 , the frequency distance (in octaves) between the first tone in the current trial and the first tone in the previous trial, measured from the fundamentals in the case of complex tones. Bias curves for consecutive trials with the same timbre category (simple: sky blue; or complex: dark blue) overlap and are substantially larger in magnitude, resembling the pattern observed with other distributions (Figure 2b–d, Figure 3a, right). By contrast, the cross-category bias magnitudes are significantly smaller and comparable to each other. Error bars indicate the standard error of the mean. **b. Bottom-up influence on pitch contraction – Pitch contraction across timbre categories is driven by frequency components that are physically present in the stimuli, even when they differ from high-level pitch perception, indicating bottom-up contraction on low level representations.** The contraction of pure tones (blue rectangle) toward complex tones with a missing fundamental (purple dashed line) within the same octave is plotted as a function of the frequency distance between the pure tone and the missing fundamental (lower inset). The bias (slope of the blue line plot) is not significantly different from zero, indicating no contraction toward the pitch of complex tones. However, higher pure tones (orange rectangle), within the contraction range of the second harmonic of the complex tone (one octave above the fundamental, red dashed line), are contracted toward the second harmonic, even though it does not correspond to the pitch. The bias driven by the second harmonic is plotted as a function of the frequency distance between the pure tone and the second harmonic (yellow line plot in the upper inset). This finding highlights an important contribution of recent low-level representations operating bottom-up on low-level representations of the current stimuli. (Adapted from Ref. [90]).

the scope of this paper, we note that contraction toward recent low-level stimulus representations, operating in a bottom-up manner, may enhance perceptual organization and underlie contraction between objects that share local features but belong to different perceptual categories [90]. In contrast, contraction toward higher-level representations, acting top-down, can be shaped by task demands, attention, perceptual categories, working memory, or decision-making processes [92].

Short- and long-term learning – Same or different mechanisms?

Tong and Dubé [93] proposed a unified model to explain recent and long-term inter-trial biases in single-item estimation tasks. The core idea is that biases from both recent and longer-term statistics are formed by integrating prior stimuli, weighted by their fidelity, as a function of time, serial position, and task-specific variables. The most recent stimuli typically have the highest fidelity, which thus leads to recency bias.

However, because the fidelity-weighted average tends to approximate the arithmetic mean, the model naturally produces a central tendency bias without explicitly incorporating a central tendency component. This model provides a general framework that is conceptually compatible with many existing models.

Physiological evidence for a shared underlying mechanism comes from Akrami et al. [94], who showed that silencing the posterior parietal cortex (PPC) during a two-tone intensity discrimination task in rats eliminated both recency bias and long-term bias effects in working memory. Boboeva et al. [95] advanced a computational model unifying these two biases, and demonstrated that recency bias naturally gives rise to a central tendency bias without requiring prior knowledge of the stimulus distribution.

Sun et al. [96] suggests that both short- and long-term priors are integrated at the perceptual, rather than decisional, level. In a task where the previous stimulus

(short-term prior) and the distribution mean (long-term prior) were placed in conflict, both sources of bias influenced participants' perceptual representations, consistent with a shared integration stage. However, the authors propose that the short-term prior reflects a transient memory trace from the previous trial, while the long-term prior results from accumulated statistical learning over many trials, suggesting different learning dynamics and possibly distinct neural substrates. Still, a key open question is whether these different time-scales rely on fundamentally separate computational systems, or whether they reflect variations in a single, flexible updating process.

Concluding remarks

Studies have only recently begun to calculate the effects of recent and long-term history on perception and perceptual learning separately within the same framework. This review shows that these calculations and the findings they generate can shed light on a variety of different situations and different tasks, and suggest that specific populations may be atypical in one and not the other, leading to different dynamics in the acquisition of basic skills. Understanding the role of perceptual history in developmental disorders may help guide more targeted interventions. For example, increasing stimulus repetitions may help compensate for the fast decay of perceptual memory observed in dyslexia, while allowing more time or slower pacing may support individuals with autism who show slower updating of recent information. While this review focused on perceptual predictions across timescales, and how reduced use of these statistics affect skill acquisition in developmental disorders, it is important to note that these disorders also involve broader cognitive differences, such as in attention and memory. Future research is needed to uncover the neural mechanisms underlying these biases and to clarify how different timescales of perceptual history interact.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that no competing interests exist.

Acknowledgments

This research was supported in part by grant NSF PHY-2309135 to the Kavli Institute for Theoretical Physics (KITP). It also received funding from the European Research Council (ERC) under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant #833694) awarded to M.A., and from the Shimon Peres Postdoctoral Fellowship awarded to A.S.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

Papers of particular interest, published within the period of review, have been highlighted as:

* of special interest

** of outstanding interest

1. Kourtzi Z, Welchman AE: **Learning predictive structure without a teacher: decision strategies and brain routes.** *Curr Opin Neurobiol* 2019, **58**:130–134.
 2. Durlach NI, Braida LD: **Intensity perception. I. Preliminary theory of intensity resolution.** *J Acoust Soc Am* 1969, **46**:372–383.
 3. Yeshurun Y, Carrasco M, Maloney LT: **Bias and sensitivity in two-interval forced choice procedures: tests of the difference model.** *Vision Res* 2008, **48**:1837–1851.
 4. Raviv O, Lieder I, Loewenstein Y, Ahissar M: **Contradictory behavioral biases result from the influence of past stimuli on perception.** *PLoS Comput Biol* 2014, **10**.
 5. Lieder I, Adam V, Frenkel O, Jaffe-Dax S, Sahani M, Ahissar M: **Perceptual bias reveals slow-updating in autism and fast-forgetting in dyslexia.** *Nat Neurosci* 2019, **22**:256–264.
 6. Hollingworth HL: **The central tendency of judgment. The journal of philosophy.** *Psychol Scientific Methods* 1910, **7**:461.
 7. Ashourian P, Loewenstein Y: **Bayesian inference underlies the contraction bias in delayed comparison tasks.** *PLoS One* 2011, **6**.
 8. Olkkonen M, McCarthy PF, Allred SR: **The central tendency bias in color perception: effects of internal and external noise.** *J Vis* 2014, **14**.
 9. Jazayeri M, Shadlen MN: **Temporal context calibrates interval timing.** *Nat Neurosci* 2010, **13**:1020–1026.
 10. Tal-Perry N, Yuval-Greenberg S: **Contraction bias in temporal estimation.** *Cognition (The Hague)* 2022, **229**.
 11. Petzschner FH, Glasauer S, Stephan KE: **A Bayesian perspective on magnitude estimation.** *Trends Cognit Sci* 2015, **19**:285–293.
 12. Tong J, Ngo V, Goldreich XD: **Tactile length contraction as Bayesian inference.** *J Neurophysiol* 2016, **116**:369–379.
 13. Xiang Y, Graeber T, Enke B, Gershman SJ: **Confidence and central tendency in perceptual judgment.** *Atten Percept Psychophys* 2021, **83**:3024–3034.
 14. Körding KP, Wolpert DM: **Bayesian integration in sensorimotor learning.** *Nature* 2004, **427**:244–247.
 15. Jaffe-Dax S, Raviv O, Jacoby N, Loewenstein Y, Ahissar M: **A computational model of implicit memory captures dyslexics' perceptual deficits.** *J Neurosci* 2015, **35**:12116–12126.
 16. Girshick AR, Landy MS, Simoncelli EP: **Cardinal rules: visual orientation perception reflects knowledge of environmental statistics.** *Nature Neuroscience* 2011, **14**:926–932.
 17. Bosker HR: **Evidence for selective adaptation and recalibration in the perception of lexical stress.** *Lang Speech* 2022, **65**:472–490.
 18. Xie X, Weatherholtz K, Bainton L, Rowe E, Burchill Z, Liu L, Jaeger TF: **Rapid adaptation to foreign-accented speech and its transfer to an unfamiliar talker.** *J Acoust Soc Am* 2018, **143**:2013–2031.
 19. Kleinschmidt DF, Jaeger TF: **Robust speech perception: recognize the familiar, generalize to the similar, and adapt to the novel.** *Psychol Rev* 2015, **122**:148–203.
 20. Manassi M, Murai Y, Whitney D: **Serial dependence in visual perception: a meta-analysis and review.** *J Vis* 2023, **23**.
- This recent review presents an operational definition of serial dependence in visual perception, identifying four key characteristics: (1) temporal-tuning, (2) spatial-tuning, (3) feature-tuning, and (4)

attention-tuning. The authors discuss these characteristics in the framework of promoting stability in the visual experience.

21. Pascucci D, Tanrikulu ÖD, Ozkirlı A, Houborg C, Ceylan G, Zerr P, Rafiei M, Kristjánsson Á: **Serial dependence in visual perception: a review.** *J Vis* 2023, **23**.
This recent review explores the experimental paradigms used to measure serial dependence and examines its core characteristics. It also addresses the potential relationship between serial dependence and the concept of "object-identity."
22. Pascucci D, Plomp G: **Serial dependence and representational momentum in single-trial perceptual decisions.** *Sci Rep* 2021, **11**.
23. Pascucci D, Mancuso G, Santandrea E, Libera C Della, Plomp G, Chelazzi L: **Laws of concatenated perception: vision goes for novelty, decisions for perseverance.** *PLoS Biol* 2019, **17**.
24. Fischer J, Whitney D: **Serial dependence in visual perception.** *Nat Neurosci* 2014, **17**:738–743.
25. Manassi M, Liberman A, Kosovicheva A, Zhang K, Whitney D: **Serial dependence in position occurs at the time of perception.** *Psychon Bull Rev* 2018, **25**:2245–2253.
26. Liberman A, Fischer J, Whitney D: **Serial dependence in the perception of faces.** *Curr Biol* 2014, **24**:2569–2574.
27. Liberman A, Manassi M, Whitney D: **Serial dependence promotes the stability of perceived emotional expression depending on face similarity.** *Atten Percept Psychophys* 2018, **80**:1461–1473.
28. Xia Y, Leib AY, Whitney D: **Serial dependence in the perception of attractiveness.** *J Vis* 2016, **16**.
29. Van der Burg E, Toet A, Brouwer AM, van Erp JBF: **Sequential effects in odor perception.** *Chemosens Percept* 2022, **15**: 19–25.
30. Arzounian D, de Kerangal M, de Cheveigné A: **Sequential dependencies in pitch judgments.** *J Acoust Soc Am* 2017, **142**: 3047–3057.
31. Chambers C, Akram S, Adam V, Pelofi C, Sahani M, Shamma S, Pressnitzer D: **Prior context in audition informs binding and shapes simple features.** *Nat Commun* 2017, **8**.
32. Motala A, Zhang H, Alais D: **Auditory rate perception displays a positive serial dependence.** *Iperception* 2020, **11**.
33. Burr D, Cicchini GM: **Vision: efficient adaptive coding.** *Curr Biol* 2014, **24**:R1096–R1098.
34. Cicchini GM, Mikellidou K, Burr DC: **The functional role of serial dependence.** *Proc Biol Sci* 2018, **285**.
35. Hastie T, Tibshirani R: **Varying-coefficient models.** *J Roy Stat Soc B* 1993, **55**:757–779.
36. Wood S: *Package 'mgcv': mixed GAM computation vehicle with automatic smoothness estimation.* CRAN; 2022.
37. Glaze CM, Kable JW, Gold JL: **Normative evidence accumulation in unpredictable environments.** *eLife* 2015, **4**.
38. Piet AT, El Hady A, Brody CD: **Rats adopt the optimal timescale for evidence integration in a dynamic environment.** *Nat Commun* 2018, **9**.
39. Piray P, Daw ND: **A model for learning based on the joint estimation of stochasticity and volatility.** *Nat Commun* 2021, **12**.
40. Charlton JA, Młynarski WF, Bai YH, Hermundstad AM, Goris RLT: **Environmental dynamics shape perceptual decision bias.** *PLoS Comput Biol* 2023, **19**.
This study suggests that people's perceptual interpretations of ambiguous sensory measurements are influenced by beliefs about the likelihood of changes in environmental statistics, thus demonstrating how perceptual biases adapt to environmental volatility.
41. Behrens TEJ, Woolrich MW, Walton ME, Rushworth MFS: **Learning the value of information in an uncertain world.** *Nat Neurosci* 2007, **10**:1214–1221.
42. Sapay-Triomphe LA, Pattyn L, Weilhhammer V, Sterzer P, Wagemans J: **Neural correlates of hierarchical predictive processes in autistic adults.** *Nat Commun* 2023, **14**.
This study investigated the neural correlates of atypical predictive mechanisms reported in individuals with autism. The authors found significant activity differences in the anterior cingulate cortex and putamen in neurotypicals compared to individuals with autism.
43. Raviv O, Ahissar M, Loewenstein Y: **How recent history affects perception: the normative approach and its heuristic approximation.** *PLoS Comput Biol* 2012, **8**.
44. Heald JB, Lengyel M, Wolpert DM: **Contextual inference underlies the learning of sensorimotor repertoires.** *Nature* 2021, **600**:489–493. 7889 2021.
45. Heald JB, Lengyel M, Wolpert DM: **Contextual inference in learning and memory.** *Trends Cognit Sci* 2023, **27**: 43–64.
This paper presents a unified framework formalizing the concept of context in learning. The authors propose a Bayesian model in which context is treated as a discrete, hidden variable that must be inferred. This contextual inference leads to differentiating between two types of learning: *proper learning*, where memory acquisition and expression occur within a known context, and *apparent learning*, where memory processes depend on the observer's uncertainty about the active context.
46. Regier DA, Kuhl EA, Kupfer DJ: **The DSM-5: classification and criteria changes.** *World Psychiatry* 2013, **12**:92–98.
47. Snowling M, Bishop DVM, Stothard SE: **Is preschool language impairment a risk factor for dyslexia in adolescence?** *J Child Psychol Psychiatry Allied Discip* 2000, **41**:587–600.
48. Ahissar M, Lubin Y, Putter-Katz H, Banai K: **Dyslexia and the failure to form a perceptual anchor.** *Nat Neurosci* 2006, **9**: 1558–1564.
49. Ahissar M: **Dyslexia and the anchoring-deficit hypothesis.** *Trends Cognit Sci* 2007, **11**:458–465.
50. Oganian Y, Ahissar M: **Poor anchoring limits dyslexics' perceptual, memory, and reading skills.** *Neuropsychologia* 2012, **50**:1895–1905.
51. Jaffe-Dax S, Frenkel O, Ahissar M: **Dyslexics' faster decay of implicit memory for sounds and words is manifested in their shorter neural adaptation.** *eLife* 2017, **6**.
52. Perrachione TK, Del Tufo SN, Winter R, Murtagh J, Cyr A, Chang P, Halverson K, Ghosh SS, Christodoulou JA, Gabrieli JDE: **Dysfunction of rapid neural adaptation in dyslexia.** *Neuron (Camb, Mass)* 2016, **92**:1383–1397.
53. Gertsovski A, Ahissar M: **Reduced learning of sound categories in dyslexia is associated with reduced regularity-induced auditory cortex adaptation.** *J Neurosci* 2022, **42**: 1328–1342.
This study indicates that individuals with dyslexia struggle with the use of sound categories due to weaker ability to adapt to repeated auditory stimuli. The authors attribute this impairment to diminished adaptation in cortical areas responsible for integrating sensory history.
54. Banai K, Ahissar M: **Poor sensitivity to sound statistics impairs the acquisition of speech categories in dyslexia.** *Lang Cogn Neurosci* 2018, **33**:321–332.
55. Gabay Y, Holt LL: **Incidental learning of sound categories is impaired in developmental dyslexia.** *Cortex* 2015, **73**:131–143.
56. Gertsovski A, Guri O, Ahissar M: **Reduced categorical learning of faces in dyslexia.** *Cortex* 2024, **173**:80–95.
This study investigated the acquisition of new face categories in dyslexia, and suggests that slower categorical learning represents a core, domain-general difficulty for individuals with dyslexia.
57. Kimel E, Daikhin L, Jakoby H, Ahissar M: **Reduced benefit from long-term item frequency contributes to short-term memory deficits in dyslexia.** *Mem Cognit* 2024, <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13421-024-01601-z>.
In this study, digit-span performance was shown to be significantly higher in the participants' native language (related to greater exposure) than in their second language (related to less exposure), suggesting that the lesser benefits derived from long-term perceptual statistics

perception. Surprisingly, the authors found that pitch contraction across different timbre categories was driven by local frequency components rather than pitch itself, thus offering new insights into the mechanisms underlying serial dependence in auditory perception.

91. Whitney D, Manassi M, Murai Y: **Searching for serial dependencies in the brain.** *PLoS Biol* 2022, **20**.
92. Kiyonaga A, Scimeca JM, Bliss DP, Whitney D: **Serial dependence across perception, attention, and memory.** *Trends Cognit Sci* 2017, **21**:493–497.
93. Tong K, Dubé C: **A tale of two literature: a fidelity-based integration account of central tendency bias and serial dependency.** *Comput Brain Behav* 2022, **5**:103–123.
** This study examined central tendency and serial dependence within a unified computational framework, and proposed that both effects stem from a common underlying process.
94. Akrami A, Kopec CD, Diamond ME, Brody CD: **Posterior parietal cortex represents sensory history and mediates its effects on behaviour.** *Nature* 2018, **554**:368–372.
95. Boboeva V, Pezzotta A, Clopath C, Akrami A: **Unifying network model links recency and central tendency biases in working memory.** *eLife* 2023, **12**.
* This study presents a unified network model to account for both central tendency and serial dependence biases within a single neural circuit. In particular, the model suggests that central tendency can emerge without the need to learn the environmental stimulus distribution, thus providing a novel approach to understanding the mechanism underlying these biases in working memory.
96. Sun Q, Wang JY, Gong XM: **Conflicts between short- and long-term experiences affect visual perception through modulating sensory or motor response systems: evidence from Bayesian inference models.** *Cognition (The Hague)* 2024, **246**, 105768.